

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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ABSTRACT

I.FAST has organized a programme of exchanges of experience and personnel between an IFAST European Accelerator Development Laboratory and a European Industrial Company, called “Industrial Training associated with Knowledge Transfer”. Initially, the exchange was focussed on training of industrial engineers and technicians at European accelerator development Laboratories, while after the first I.FAST project review (P1), it was widened to include transfer of knowledge through exchange of personnel and experience in both directions, between a Laboratory and a Company. The report summarizes the six exchange programs supported and their outcomes.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

I.FAST has announced the availability of a grant to support an exchange programme for knowledge, expertise, and working practices concerning new accelerator and magnet component technologies between an I.FAST European Accelerator Development Laboratory and a European Industrial Company.

This programme has enabled companies to send personnel to one of the I.FAST Laboratories, with reciprocal exchanges also possible.

By fostering collaboration between research laboratories and industrial companies, this exchange programme aims to bridge the gap between cutting-edge scientific research and practical industrial applications. Participants in the programme benefit from hands-on experience with advanced accelerator and magnet technologies, gaining insights into both theoretical concepts and operational best practices. Companies and Laboratories have been encouraged to identify staff members and students whose professional development would be enhanced by exposure to state-of-the-art laboratory or industry environments.

Overall, the I.FAST exchange programme has represented an important initiative to promote innovation, accelerate technological progress, and strengthen ties between academia and industry across Europe and it has supported six exchanges here described.

1 Introduction

The IFAST Task 2.4 created since the beginning of the project (2021) the possibility to apply for a grant to finance a programme of exchange of knowledge, expertise, and working practices of new accelerator and magnet component technologies between an I.FAST European Accelerator Development Laboratory (here called the IFAST Laboratory) and a European Industrial Company (here called the Company). The initiative called “I.FAST Academia-Industry Exchange Programme” has been announced on the I.FAST website (<https://ifast-project.eu/ifast-traineeship-programme>) in all I.FAST meetings and at several conferences of the accelerator community.

After the first Periodic Report (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1232185/>) the program was extended in scope and re-issued since it turned out not to be attractive for industry participants. It offered the opportunity for a Company to send an engineer or technician for one or several visits to one of the IFAST Laboratories and for a IFAST Laboratory to send a scientist, engineer or technician to a Company for one or several visits.

It has been possible to apply for a grant of up to 7000 € per person (after P1 reporting the limit was increased to 9000 €) for financing such a technical exchange programme which should put emphasis on transfer between the two parties of knowledge, expertise, and working practices of design, fabrication and testing of new advanced technological components for frontline accelerator and magnet research and/or technology infrastructures.

The grants have been used to finance salary costs, travel and subsistence for the engineers, technicians or PhD students during their visits.

The proposal needed to be jointly submitted by the IFAST Laboratory and the Company, describing on a maximum of 2 pages:

1. The project and the technology with which the engineers and technicians shall work at the IFAST Laboratory and/or at the Company;
2. How this work will lead to sharing of knowledge of new component technology between the IFAST Laboratory and the Company;
3. A brief budget showing how the IFAST Laboratory and at the Company intend to use the IFAST grant;
4. How the Company and the IFAST Laboratory intend to make use of the expertise exchanged, for business and/or research purposes.

1.1 THE SELECTION PROCESS

The applications have been judged by the IFAST Knowledge Exchange Selection Committee based on the:

1. Relevance of the interest of the Company and/or the IFAST Laboratory to exchange expertise of the technology.
2. Professional merits of the proposed scientists, engineers and/or technicians that will make the technical visits.
3. Level of knowledge and experience of the IFAST Laboratory and of the Company of the associated component technology.
4. The quality and effectiveness of the exchange program being proposed.
5. Consistency between the proposed exchange activity with the amount of salary, travel and subsistence support requested for the engineers and/or technicians and the proposed program of visits.
6. The expected outcomes of the technology transfer of the exchange project.
7. The proposed terms of the agreement on the exchange programme between the Laboratory and the Company.

The IFAST Laboratory and the Company were requested to jointly submit a brief report to the IFAST Knowledge Exchange Selection Committee at the end of the exchange programme, detailing the outcomes of the exchange, particularly with respect to knowledge transfer.

The composition of the Selection Committee is given in Appendix 2.

2 The exchange programmes between TFs and Industrial companies

In the following section a concise description of the six exchange programmes between IFAST Laboratory and the Industrial Companies is given together with the relative outcomes.

2.1 THE FREIA-LEIJNAAR TRAINEESHIP PROGRAMME

I.FAST Laboratory	Industrial Company
<p style="text-align: center;"><i>FREIA/ Uppsala Universitet</i> Lägerhyddsvägen 1 751 20 Uppsala Sweden</p> <p>Contact person: Dragos Dancila</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Leijenaar Electronics</i> Dionisiusstraat 9 5808 CA Oirlo The Netherlands</p> <p>Contact person: William Leijenaar</p>
<p>Exchanged person</p> <p>W. Leijenaar (<i>Leijenaar Electronics</i>)</p> <p>Cost: 6000 EUR, travel costs, salary and prototype manufacturing during the stay at Uppsala University</p>	

The traineeship in the FREIA Laboratory at Uppsala University of Mr. William Leijenaar, former engineer at the Ampleon semiconductor company in the Netherlands and founder of his own technical consulting company, regards the development of a 400-kW solid-state power amplifier (SSPA) station that is presently being developed at the FREIA laboratory.

This project has covered different aspects of large power radiofrequency (RF) stations: solid state power transistors (an SSPA with a total of 1.5 kW power have been realized during the internship), power combiners and controls and is of high relevance for the trainee and his future activities in this area.

The programme is concluded and the trainee has learned more about the challenges and opportunities related to the development at FREIA Laboratory of large SSPA RF systems used in particle accelerators.

2.2 THE CERN-PERCYROK EXCHANGE PROGRAMME

I.FAST Laboratory	Industrial Company
<p style="text-align: center;">CERN Espl. des Particules 1 1217 Genève Switzerland</p> <p>Contact person: Steffen Doebert, Ben Woolley</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">PERCY ROC AB Green Innovation Park Ulls väg 29C, 756 51 Uppsala Sweden</p> <p>Contact person: Kristiaan Pelckmans</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Exchanged person</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Kristiaan Pelckmans (PERCY ROC) Cost: 8750 € for travel costs and salary during the stay at CERN</p>	

The Company has been working for last 1.5 year on an implementation of the Low Level RF (LLRF) control system based on a microTCA embedded system for enabling the explorations of advanced RF systems at CERN and at Uppsala University (UU) in the context of the next iteration of the AWAKE (‘wakefield acceleration’) project.

This effort fits within the wider AWAKE collaboration between CERN and Uppsala University. This expertise development benefits the SME (‘Percy Roc’) due to similarities between the technologies and processes used here and those employed in its core business (‘Industrial microwave heating’), with the following objectives:

- identifying openings for further innovation,
- gathering experience and credibility in the state-of-art LLRF systems,
- prepare for meeting emerging challenges towards automatic control and energy-aware processing.

The project has reached completion. Uppsala University has successfully developed and delivered a prototype low-level RF control system (LLRF) to CERN through the participation of Percy Roc, and the system is currently undergoing testing at CERN.

A 3 GHz 400W solid state amplifier has been developed and delivered to CERN, with two additional units currently in assembly. The collaboration between CERN and Uppsala has ended as all allocated funds have been expended.

2.3 SEEIIST-COSYLAB EXCHANGE PROGRAMMEE

I.FAST Laboratory	Industrial Company
<p><i>The South East European International Institute for Sustainable Technologies (SEEIIST)</i> SEEIIST C/O PKF Fiduciaire Rue de Battoirs 7, 1205 Geneve Switzerland</p> <p>Contact person: Peter Gruebling, CEO</p>	<p><i>Cosylab Switzerland GmbH</i> Förderstiftung Technopark Aargau Badenerstrasse 13, 5200 Brugg Switzerland</p> <p>Contact person: Conor Slater, GM</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Exchanged person</p> <p style="text-align: center;">L. Garolfi (SEEIIST, CERN)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Cost: 8750 €, for salary during the stay (2 months) – full cost including overheads.</p>	

The South East European International Institute for Sustainable Technologies (SEEIIST) Association is building a state-of-the-art facility for cancer hadron therapy and biomedical research in the SEE countries. Cosylab is the leading provider of software solutions for the world’s most complex, precise, and advanced systems. Their technology enables organisations to discover scientific breakthroughs, offer state-of-the-art cancer treatment and healthcare innovations, and bring clean fusion power to the future energy market.

The project aims to prepare a comprehensive product design specification documentation for an innovative gantry-less, compact, and high-performance proton therapy facility. The specification will focus on advanced cancer treatment while reducing the physical footprint and costs compared to traditional gantry-based systems.

This collaboration has created a dynamic environment for growth, innovation, and the development of more cost-effective cancer treatments. The project facilitated technical exchanges, allowing researchers and engineers from both sides to share knowledge on new component technologies and advancements in proton therapy. It promoted a deeper understanding of the field and facilitated the integration of cutting-edge technologies into a cost-effective and efficient facility design.

2.4 THE RTU-RÖSLER EXCHANGE PROGRAMMEE

I.FAST Laboratory	Industrial Company
<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Riga Technical University (RTU)</i> 6A Kipsalas Street, Riga, LV-1048 Latvia</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Contact person: Andris Ratkus <i>e-mail: andris.ratkus@rtu.lv</i></p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Rösler Italiana S.R.L.</i> Via Elio Vittorini 10/12, 20863 Concorezzo Italy</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Contact person: Conor Pozzi, GM <i>e-mail: M.Pozzi@rosler.com</i></p>
<p>Exchanged person:</p> <p>T. Romano (<i>Riga Technical University</i>) Cost: 8550 EUR, salary for 3 months during stay</p>	

The project is to develop linear accelerating structures for ion injection into a cancer therapy synchrotron and parallel production of radioisotopes. It focuses on investigating post-processing techniques for additively manufactured pure copper Radio Frequency Quadrupole (RFQ) elements, with a particular emphasis on the vane tips. Initial research on RFQ post-processing has shown promising results. The limited accessibility of the vane tips presents challenges for both treatment and measurement, necessitating further in-depth study.

This research aims to define the specific post-processing requirements and evaluate the feasibility of achieving precise dimensional accuracy and optimal surface roughness for the vane tips. A specialised testing apparatus will be developed and produced to evaluate various post-processing methodologies and process parameters, closely replicating full-scale, real component conditions through mass finishing techniques, both with and without the use of chemical additives.

2.5 THE CERN-OCEM EXCHANGE PROGRAMMEE

I.FAST Laboratory	Industrial Company
<p>CERN, TERA-CARE CH1211 Geneva 23 Switzerland</p> <p>Contact person: Maurizio Vretenar</p>	<p>OCEM Power electronics Switzerland GmbH Via della Solidarietà, 2/1 40056, Valsamoggia (BO) Italy</p> <p>Contact person: Miguel Pretelli</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Exchanged person</p> <p style="text-align: center;">A. Cassar (<i>TERA-CARE, Project Associate at CERN</i>) Cost: 3000 EUR, travel and lodging at Bologna for one month</p>	

The goal of this project is to optimise the design of a power converter in combination with a medical accelerator dipole magnet, to achieve the highest possible energy and time efficiency, while ensuring ease of installation and maintenance.

A baseline magnet design already exists, with preliminary power calculations completed. This project refines and adapts such design to meet the specific operational requirements of a medical facility.

The project to be carried out by Ariana Cassar, presently based at CERN, will be part of her PhD work that is ongoing in collaboration between CERN, TERA-CARE and the student’s home University, the University of Malta.

The project will address the following areas of optimisation, among others:

- Power Converter Technology:
 - Selecting technology for improved efficiency, durability, and scalability
- Magnet Powering Configuration:
 - Evaluating different powering schemes: in series, individually, or in pairs.
- Magnet Cycle Optimisation and improvements
 - : Refining ramp rates to minimise energy consumption and cycle time
 - Optimising the number of turns per coil to balance inductance, resistance, and peak/average power demands (optional)

This project will combine OCEM’s expertise in power converter design for accelerator and industrial applications with the novel requirements for a compact and energy efficient medical accelerator that is being designed in collaboration between CERN and TERA-CARE.

Power converters are typically designed according to the specifications of the magnet and the operational cycle. Referring to historical data from comparable applications for performance evaluations, as well as conducting joint design reviews, can assist in identifying applicable methods and developing technical solutions aimed at optimising both magnet and power converter designs. This collaboration will support OCEM in developing systems with improved performance and energy efficiency, while CERN and TERA-CARE will receive industrial feedback to facilitate the application of research results in practical contexts.

OCEM, CERN and TERA-CARE will integrate their knowledge and expertise to advance the co-design of accelerator magnets and power converter solutions with improved energy efficiency, operational reliability and maintainability.

OCEM will benefit from insights to refine their product portfolio and strengthening their position in the market. CERN and TERA-CARE will benefit from improved competences and training opportunities for researchers and students, and improved design guidelines to develop solutions that are more practical to implement in future projects and across the wider scientific community.

3 Appendix 1: Example of a full exchange programme summary

In the following section is reported, as an example, the full summary of the exchange program between SEEIST and Cosylab (see section 2.4).

I.FAST Academia-industry exchange programme summary

Laboratory: SEEIST Association
Company: Cosylab Switzerland GmbH
Applicant: Luca Garolfi (SEEIST Association)

Contact person: Peter Gruebling, CEO
Contact person: Conor Slater, GM

The I.FAST academia-industry exchange programme has been between SEEIST / CERN NIMMS (an I.FAST Laboratory) and Cosylab Switzerland GmbH (the Company).

Cosylab collaborated with the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI) to commercialise its Proton Therapy (PT) technology. Cosylab planned to enhance its services and market position. It gained a comprehensive definition of the technical requirements for the treatment equipment, beam delivery system, and treatment planning system, which will ultimately guide the implementation of a cost-effective and efficient advanced cancer treatment facility. PSI has designed an innovative gantry-less, compact, and high-performance PT facility integrating a recent beam momentum cooling innovation enabling significant beam transmission to the patient. It was interested in a reliable facility cost breakdown of the main accelerator components, systems, and sub-systems for an overall capital cost assessment as a proposal to possible future investors.

SEEIST/ CERN NIMMS sought to incorporate industry practices and advancements into the proton medical accelerators research, defining technical requirements for the treatment equipment, especially in beam delivery systems, and critical operational beam parameters to compare with more complex heavier ions synchrotron technology, ensuring accurate treatment delivery standards.

Cosylab profited from Dr. Luca Garolfi's background and expertise in accelerator design, components, and machine operation to successfully collaborate with PSI researchers. He analysed high-level engineering requirements and reported them in a comprehensive product design specification documentation with detailed technical parameters, characteristics, and performances of the accelerator components, systems, and sub-systems. Also, Dr. Garolfi prepared an accurate Bill of Materials (BOM) documentation for the high-level architecture of the facility. Furthermore, he paved the context for a structured capital cost breakdown by analysing the business case and comparing it with existing commercial systems from top-down and bottom-up approaches.

Dr. Garolfi, on behalf of SEEIST/NIMMS CERN, gained experience in many industrial medical project aspects, such as the relation with the scientific stakeholder, knowledge of the efficient and compact PT

facility design, the identification of technical requirements for the treatment equipment, including the proton accelerator, beam delivery system, and treatment planning system, proton energy range, beam spot size, and intensity modulation capabilities to ensure accurate treatment delivery, valuable insights about patient preparation, imaging, rigorous criteria of writing a comprehensive product design specification and Bill of Materials (BOM) documentation according to the standards, structured business case, and cost comparison with similar commercial products.

This collaboration has created a dynamic environment for growth, innovation, and the development of more cost-effective cancer treatments. The project facilitated technical exchanges, allowing researchers and engineers from both sides to share knowledge on new component technologies and advancements in proton therapy. It promoted a deeper understanding of the field and facilitated the integration of cutting-edge technologies into a cost-effective and efficient facility design.

4 Appendix 2: I.FAST Committees

Two committees have been established by the I.FAST governing board within the first six months of the project: the Industrial Advisory Board (<https://ifast-project.eu/industrial-advisory-board>) to help the project to make fruitful the interactions among I.FAST Laboratories and Companies and the I.FAST Knowledge Exchange Selection Committee for the selection of applications submitted.

The members of the two committees are hereinafter reported:

Name	Role	Company	Country
Angeles Faus-Golfe	Chair	CNRS/IN2P3	Spain
Miguel Angel Carrera	Member	AVS - Added Value Solutions	Spain
Francesco Fantini	Member	Fantini Sud S.p.A.	Italy
Pavel Hedbavny	Member	Vakuum Praha	Czechia
Rok Hrovatin	Member	Cosylab	Slovenia
Olivier Tasset-Maye	Member	Sigmaphi	France
Charles Mangeot	Member	CTS Corporation	Denmark
Ziad Melhem	Member	Oxford Quantum Solutions Ltd	United Kingdom
Michael Pekeler	Member	Research-Instruments	Germany
François Sylla	Member	SourceLAB - Laser Plasma Technologies	France
Josef Troxler	Member	Ampegon & OCEM Power Electronics AG	Switzerland

Table 1: Members of Industrial Advisory Board

Name	Role	Institution/ Company	Country
Tord Ekelöf	Chair	Uppsala University	Sweden
Antoine Le Gall	Member	CERN	Switzerland
Philip Burrows	Member	Oxford University	United Kingdom
Sylvie Leray	Member	CEA Saclay	France
Spela Stres	Member	Jozef Stefan Institute	Slovenia
Ziad Melhem	Member	Oxford Quantum Solutions Ltd	United Kingdom
Francesco Fantini	Member	Fantini Sud S.p.A.	Italy

Table 1: Members of I.FAST Knowledge Exchange Selection Committee

The member Antoine Le Gall (CERN, Switzerland) has been replaced in October 2023 by Thomas Brent (CERN, Switzerland).